

1 **Compounds responsible for off-odors in several samples composed by**
2 **polypropylene, polyethylene, paper and cardboard used as food packaging materials**

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13

14 **Abstract**

15 Seven commercial samples, consisted of plastic bags, tetrabrik and box, were evaluated
16 by gas chromatography-olfactometry-mass spectrometry (GC-O-MS) to find the
17 compounds responsible for off-odors in different PP, PE, multilayer cardboard and paper
18 materials used for food contact. Migration assays were carried out with Tenax as food
19 simulant to analyze the food safety as well as to evaluate the odor intensity after migration
20 assay. Forty six compounds with characteristic odors were directly found in the materials
21 studied. The strongest odors identified were acetic, propanoic and butyric with vinegar
22 and rancid odors and octanal, nonanal and decanal with fat/soup odors, all of them found
23 in PP and PE samples. Trimethylbenzenes with solvent and oily odors as well as terpenes
24 with weakly woody odors were found in cardboard and paper materials. After migration,
25 all compounds were bellow the European Legislation limits and maximum migration
26 values recommended by Cramer. However propanoic, acetic and butyric acid as well as
27 aldehydes compounds, phenol and 1-octanol were detected by sniffers, after migration

28 assay, with high modified frequency (between 50 and 78 %), what could change the
29 organoleptic properties of packaged food

30

31 **1. Introduction**

32 The main function of food packaging is a correct food preservation to guarantee food
33 safety and quality. The safety is ensured avoiding the chemical contamination due to the
34 transfer of compounds from the packaging to the food. This phenomenon called migration
35 has been widely studied for different materials such as adhesives (Canellas, Vera, &
36 Nerin, 2014, 2016; Nerin, Gaspar, Vera, Canellas, Aznar, & Mercea, 2013), plastic
37 materials like polypropylene, polyethylene, polyester and cardboard for food contact
38 (Chang, Kang, Park, Choi, Kim, & Han, 2019; Paseiro-Cerrato, DeJager, & Begley, 2019;
39 Rubio, Valverde-Som, Sarabia, & Ortiz, 2019; Ubeda, Aznar, Vera, Nerin, Henriquez,
40 Taborda, et al., 2017; Vera, Canellas, & Nerin, 2018). This chemical transfer is a major
41 concern to the packaging industry which may produce rejection's consumer and
42 millenaries losses.

43 To guarantee this safety, the materials in contact with food must fulfill the European
44 Regulation N° 1935/2004 ("Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament
45 and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into
46 contact with food and repealing Directives 80/590/EEC and 89/109/EEC,") about
47 materials in contact with food. European Regulation 10/2011/EU ("COMMISSION
48 REGULATION (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles
49 intended to come into contact with food,") details the maximum amount of a single
50 substance that can be transferred from plastic materials to the food, specific migration
51 limits (SML) as well as the conditions of time, temperature and type of simulant to carry
52 out the migration assay. Paper and Board are not harmonized as food packaging materials
53 in Europe. However, there are recommendations in the proposal approved by the Council
54 of Europe (CoE) (CoE 2002) that contains the list of substances, migration tests and
55 specific migration limits of some contaminants.

56 The food quality is mainly obtained avoiding the changes in organoleptic properties and
57 the loss of nutritive compounds. These organoleptic changes may be produced by the
58 interaction between the packaging with the food, adding new off-odors that may come

59 simply from composition of the material used (Czerny, 2017; Czerny & Buettner, 2009;
60 Osorio, Aznar, & Nerin, 2019) or may be derived from the degradation products after
61 manufacturing process, like irradiation (Salafranca, Clemente, Isella, Nerin, & Bosetti,
62 2015; Tyapkova, Czerny, & Buettner, 2009) or high temperatures exposure (Kontominas,
63 Goulas, Badeka, & Nerantzaki, 2006), all of them producing a negative effect on the
64 quality of packaged food.

65 In the food industry the quality control of odors is carried out by a sensory analysis usually
66 performed by a trained panel, where an overall perception about the presence or absence
67 of off-odors can be determined by the panelists. However, this methodology is no valid
68 to determine individual odors coming from individual compounds.

69 The technique GC-O-MS is a methodology which allows us to detect individual odor
70 compounds simultaneously by two detectors: one sniffing port with the human nose
71 which acts as an odor detector and mass spectrometry detector. It means that a compound
72 can be detected and defined by chemical and sensorial way at the same time. The human
73 nose is a detector often much more sensitive than the MS detector, capable of detecting
74 compounds with very low concentrations, even below the limit of detections obtained by
75 mass spectrometry (Brattoli, de Gennaro, de Pinto, Loiotile, Lovascio, & Penza, 2011).
76 Therefore, is capable of detecting odorous migrants which are usually at very low
77 concentrations.

78 Thus, the main objective of this work was to determine the compounds responsible for
79 the off-odor in different food contact materials, prioritizing those compounds which could
80 affect with more intensity the packaged food. Most of solid foodstuffs have adsorbent
81 properties and thus they can absorb odors from the packaging. Paper and board are well-
82 known as responsible for off-odors and the packaged food could be negatively influenced
83 by these off-odors. For this reason, in this work several packaging materials usually
84 applied to dry foods or using paper and board were selected.

85 This work was divided in different tasks (1) to run a sensory analysis in order to describe
86 the undesirable sensory attributes and their intensities in the different market materials
87 (2) to get different profiles of odorous compounds of each material by GC-O-MS looking
88 for the relation-ship with the sensory attributes found above (3) to carry out migration
89 assays of each material, not only to quantify the likely mass transfer of odorous

90 compounds in terms of possible human risk, but also, to evaluate the odor intensity of
91 each migrant previously detected. This way, the suspect compounds that could change
92 the organoleptic properties of the packed food would be identified.

93

94 **2. Materials and methods**

95 *2.1. Reagents*

96 Toluene (108-88-3), hexanal (66-25-1), b-pinene (127-91-3), ethyl benzene (100-41-4),
97 p-xylene (106-42-3), o-xylene (95-47-6), limonene (138-86-3), 1,2,4-trimethyl benzene
98 (95-63-6), octanal (124-13-0), 1,3,5-trimethyl benzene (108-67-8), cyclohexanone (108-
99 94-1), 1,2,3-trimethyl benzene (526-73-8), 4,5-dimethyl thiazole (3581-91-7), 1-octanol
100 (111-87-5), nonanal (124-19-6), acetic acid (64-19-7), furfural (98-01-1), durene (95-93-
101 2), decanal (112-31-2), 2-ethyl-1-hexanol (104-76-7), propanoic acid (79-09-4),
102 benzaldehyde (100-52-7), 2-undecanone (112-12-9), butyric acid (107-92-6), Benzoic
103 acid (65-85-0), anisole (100-66-3), 4-methyl-benzaldehyde (104-87-0), estragole (140-
104 67-0), acetophenone (98-86-2), 4-ethyl-benzaldehyde (4748-78-1), verbenone (1196-01-
105 6), naphthalene (91-20-3), 4-isopropyl-benzaldehyde (122-03-2), 4-phenyl-1-
106 cyclohexene (4994-16-5), 2-tridecanone (593-08-8), benzenemethanol, α -methyl (98-85-
107 1), 3,4-dimethylacetophenone (3637-01-2), 4-ethylacetophenone (937-30-4),
108 methylnaphthalene (90-12-0) tridecanol (112-70-9), phenol (128-95-2), 3-phenyl-2-
109 propenal (104-55-2), m-cresol (108-39-4), tetradecanol (112-72-1), nonanoic acid (122-
110 05-0), isophthalaldehyde (626-19-7) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Química S.A
111 (Madrid, Spain). All of them were of analytical quality with purity > 98%. Ethanol, water
112 and methanol of HPLC grade were supplied by Scharlau Chemie S.A (Sentmenat, Spain).
113 Tenax TA 80/100 mesh was supplied by Supelco (Bellefonte, USA).

114 *2.2. Market samples*

115 Different types of samples consisting of five bags, one tetrabrik and one cardboard box
116 used as food packaging materials were studied. They were made of different types of
117 plastics (polypropylene and polyethylene), cardboard and paper without inks. All
118 materials were from different European companies which manufacture different types of
119 materials for food contact.

120 All of them were commercial samples used for different packaging purposes which had
121 been returned from the market due to odor problems. Their final use were to package
122 vegetables like tomatoes, dried whole fruits, others for pasta like macaroni, spaghetti, also
123 for pastry products like cereals, biscuits, flour or bread or for sugar and eggs. Even though
124 the selection of materials was limited, they could represent those materials more prone to
125 be affected by off-odors. As was above mentioned, most of solid foodstuffs have
126 adsorbent properties, what means that if off-odors are produced by the packaging
127 materials, these foods would be affected. All materials under study corresponded to
128 different claims for off-odor from customers

129 Table 1 shows the samples analyzed, the materials used and their final purposes

130 *2.3. Sensory analysis*

131 A sensory evaluation was carried out by six assessors (4 female and 2 male) previously
132 trained for these type of samples. For this analysis, 1 dm² of each material (PP, PE,
133 cardboard and paper) were placed in opaque glass vessels of 50 mL of capacity. Then,
134 the panelists were asked to describe the characteristic odor of each material as well as the
135 intensity of these attributes with a scale of 1 unit (level perception) to 3 unit (strong
136 perception). This assay was carried out in a room at 20 °C.

137 After that, the data of each material were averaged and performed in three spider diagrams
138 where the values were grouped by type of material studied (PP, PE and cardboard-paper)

139

140 *2.4. GC-O-MS*

141 Chromatograph Agilent Technologies 7820A system (Madrid, Spain) coupled to 5977B
142 MSN series mass selective detector and sniffing port supplied by GL Sciences B.V
143 (Eindhoven, Netherlands) were used for the identification and migration of odor
144 compounds.

145 Chromatographic separations were carried out on a BP-20 column (30mx0.25
146 mmx0.25µm) from SGE analytical science (Madrid, Spain). The oven temperature
147 program was from 40 °C (5 min), a ramp of temperature of 10°C/min to a final temperature
148 of 220°C maintained for 10 min. Helium was used as carrier gas at 1 mL/min flow.

149 Acquisition was carried out in SCAN mode (50-450 m/z) for screening analysis and SIM
150 mode for migration quantifications. The transfer line of the olfactometer was maintained
151 at 200 °C and the sniffing port humidified with air.

152 HS-SPME injection was used for the identification of odor compounds, extracting 1 dm²
153 of each material placed into a 20 mL vial. The fiber used for this purpose was
154 DVD/CAR/PDMS of (50/30µm) thickness due to its high capacity of extraction of odor
155 compounds demonstrated in previous works (Vera, Uliaque, Canellas, Escudero, &
156 Nerin, 2012; Wrona, Vera, Pezo, & Nerin, 2017). The extraction conditions were as
157 follows, 50°C extraction temperature, 15 min extraction time and 2.5 min desorption time
158 at 250 °C.

159 One µL of migration extract was injected in splitless mode at 250°C for the migration
160 assays.

161

162 *2.5. Identification of odorous compounds from these materials*

163 To determine the odorous compounds, one dm² of each material was cut and placed in
164 20mL vials for HS-SPME extract with the conditions above described.

165 Six trained panelists sniffed the individual odorous compounds eluted from the GC
166 column, described their odors and assigned intensities. These intensities were quantified
167 using a scale from 1 to 3 units. The value of 1 corresponded to a weak odor (low intensity),
168 2 was a medium intensity and 3 corresponded to strong intensity of odor.

169 In order to highlight the most important odorous compounds of each sample, the modified
170 frequency MF (%) was calculated following the equation, $MF(\%) = [F(\%) \times I(\%)]^{0.5}$.
171 Where F(%) corresponded to the percentage of sniffers that had detected each odor
172 compound and I(%) was the average of the values of intensity written down by all the
173 sniffers divided by three (Dravnieks, 1985, 354; Vera, Uliaque, Canellas, Escudero, &
174 Nerin, 2012). All the odorous compounds with a MF value higher than 40 were
175 considered as the most important representative compounds of each material and they
176 were called “odorous market”.

177 Afterwards, the identification of each “odorous market” was carried out using the NIST
178 and WILEY mass spectra libraries as well as the use of a literature search. For this

179 purpose, KI (kovat indexes), previously calculated, and organoleptic characteristics of
180 “odorous market” were compared to the compounds with the same descriptions found in
181 the literature, for example in the web page www.flavornet.org or in previous works (Vera,
182 Uliaque, Canellas, Escudero, & Nerin, 2012; Wrona, Vera, Pezo, & Nerin, 2017)

183 Finally, to confirm the identification, these standards were injected under the same
184 chromatographic conditions (GC-O-MS), matching their retention indexes, odor
185 characteristics and mass spectra with “odorous market” under study.

186

187 *2.6. Migration assays and risk assessment.*

188 Migration assays of these materials were carry out using Tenax ® as food simulant,
189 according to Commission Regulation 10/2011/EU on plastic materials intended to come
190 into contact with food("COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January
191 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food,"). In this
192 legislation, Tenax simulant must be used as simulant for plastic materials that will be used
193 to package dry food as is the case in this study.

194 On the other hand, the proposal approved by CoE for paper and board materials also
195 recommends Tenax as simulant for migration tests due to their incompatibilities with
196 liquid simulants. For this purpose, 1 x 4 cm cutouts of each material were placed in Petri
197 dishes and covered with 0.16 grams of Tenax forming a uniform layer (4 g Tenax per dm²
198 in accordance with UNE-EN-14338 ("UNE-EN 14338:2004. Papel y cartón para contacto
199 alimentario. Condiciones para la determinación de la migración en papel y cartón
200 utilizando óxido de polifenileno modificado (MPPO) como simulante,."). Then, this
201 system was kept in an oven at 60 °C for 10 days. Afterwards, Tenax was extracted two
202 consecutive times with 1 mL of ethanol and analyzed by GC-O-MS (Vera, Canellas, &
203 Nerin, 2013; Vera, Uliaque, Canellas, Escudero, & Nerin, 2012).

204 Then, two different assays were carried out. In the first one, the same panelists sniffed
205 back the migration samples eluted from the chromatographic column to check out if they
206 were capable to detect the odor compounds identified previously and then, to calculate
207 back their modified frequencies (MF%) and then, to highlight the compounds which
208 could affect and change the organoleptic properties of the packaged food.

209 And the second one, the migrant odor concentrations were calculated in order to check
210 the possible human risks. For this purpose, firstly the migration values were expressed in
211 mg/Kg of simulant, considering the absolute mg migrated divided by the 0.08 dm² used
212 in the migration test and also, the relation 6dm² / 1Kg of simulant (regulation
213 10/2011/EU) ("COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011
214 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food,").

215 Then, these migrant values were compared with their SML belonging the positive list of
216 the legislation 10/2011/EU of plastics ("COMMISSION REGULATION (EU)
217 No 10/2011 of 14 January 2011 on plastic materials and articles intended to come into
218 contact with food,"). When the compound was not legislated, it was applied the maximum
219 values of human daily intake recommended by Cramer ("Threshold of toxicological
220 concern (TTC). ILSI Europe concise monograph series (2005) "), that establishes these
221 values depending on the theoretical toxicity of each compound based on their structures
222 and according to software Toxtree®. It classifies the compounds into three categories,
223 from Class I, low toxicity, to class III, high toxicity setting their daily intakes
224 recommended into 1.8, 0.54 and 0.09 mg/Kg for class I, II and III respectively ("Risk
225 Assessment of non-listed substances (NLS) and not-intentionally added substances
226 (NIAS) under article19 of Plastic Europe ").

227

228 **3. Results**

229 *3.1. Sensory evaluation*

230 The sensory evaluations are shown in figure 1. Three spider diagrams, each one for each
231 type of material (PP, PE and cardboard-paper) are plot with their characteristic odors and
232 their intensities.

233 For PP samples (Figure 1a), the attributes as plastic, fat/soap and rancid were perceived
234 at high intensity. In addition, moss/green and sweet/fruity presented a lower intensity and
235 tar very weakly detectable. The sample PP1 was characterized besides of plastic odor
236 (value 2.2 of intensity) by high rancid odor (1.7 of intensity). Moss aroma lower than 1
237 was perceived. Similar tendency was found for PP3, with a highest intensity to rancid
238 odor and a value of 2.3 and 2 for plastic odor. By contrast, the PP2 sample showed soft

239 attributes mainly like plastic (1.5 of intensity) and moss (1.3 of intensity). Finally, the
240 sample PP4 had the highest attributes, with values of 2.5 for plastic odor, 2.4 for fat and
241 soap odor and around 1 for sweet/fruity and floral intensities. Some panelists found in
242 this sample a weak tar odor.

243 The attributes perceived for the PE materials are shown in Figure 1b. These perceptions
244 were fewer than for PP samples. In PE1 besides of plastic odor, a severe fat/soap odor
245 was found. Also, a weak floral was detected in this material. The sample PE2 was
246 characterized by a new moderate vinegar odor (1.3 of intensity) besides of mild sweet and
247 floral odors.

248 Finally, the characteristic odors for cardboards and paper materials are illustrated in
249 Figure 1c. The sensory tests showed that these samples can exhibit high odor potency
250 while providing a large number of attributes with high intensity. Cardboard 1, besides of
251 cardboard like odor, insensitive woody and oily odors were perceived (1.9 and 1.5
252 respectively). Other important attributes found with values around of 1 were fat/soap,
253 solvent and green. It can be observed that both cardboards had similar smell profiles with
254 some intensity values lower in cardboard 2 than in cardboard 1. For paper, the main
255 characteristic odors found were fat/soap, green and cardboard like (1.7, 1.2 and 1.1 of
256 intensity respectively).

257

258 *3.2. Identification of odorous compounds.*

259 Figure 2 shows the chromatogram of Cardboard 1 material analyzed by GC-O-MS, where
260 the compounds with odor characteristics are highlighted with numbers and named in
261 Table 2. As this figure shows, sixteen odorous compounds were found in this material,
262 although the concentration of most of them were close to their detection limits and their
263 peaks do not appear with clarity.

264 Forty six compounds with characteristic odors whose MF (%) >40 were found in the
265 different materials studied. They are shown in Table 2 and ordered by their retention
266 indices.

267 The most common compounds found in different materials were nonanal, 2-ethyl-1-
268 hexanol, benzaldehyde, acetophenone and naphthalene. Nonanal was described as fat,

269 citrus and green odors descriptors and it was defined with MF (%) higher than 70 in all
270 materials. In bibliography, it is a very common compound, already detected in a lot of
271 materials of polypropylene and cardboard (Czerny, 2017; Czerny & Buettner, 2009;
272 Tyapkova, Czerny, & Buettner, 2009) and also like a thermal oxidation product in
273 polyethylene (Wiedmer, Velasco-Schon, & Buettner, 2017).

274 2-ethyl-1-hexanol with a green odor is produced on a massive scale as solvent or also as
275 precursor for production of plasticizers. Benzaldehyde (fruity, almond and cherry odor)
276 can be obtained like an off-odor compound from recycled cardboard (*Handbook of odor*,
277 2017) as well as acetophenone with almond and flower odor. This last compound can be
278 also used as component of coatings and inks. Finally naphthalene, with tar odor, may be
279 detected in articles of daily use, foods and toys (Wiedmer, Velasco-Schon, & Buettner,
280 2017). All of them were detected in most of the samples, but their MF (%) was lower than
281 65 (%) in all materials. It means that most of the panelists were capable of detecting these
282 compounds but not with high values of intensities.

283 The different compounds detected can be organized by different families. For example,
284 aldehyde family constituted by compounds such as hexanal, octanal, nonanal and decanal
285 all having a similar characteristic odors that corresponded to fat, soap, citrus. All of them
286 had great values of MF (%) with values ranging between (72-92 %). They may be the
287 responsible compounds for what the attributes fat/soup found in sensory evaluation for
288 the samples PP4, PE1, Paper 1 and cardboard 1, as shown in Figure 1 (values 2.4, 1.6, 1.7
289 and 0.9 respectively).

290 Other aldehydes found were 4-methyl, 4-ethyl and p-propyl benzaldehyde with cherry,
291 fruity and oily odors respectively. Besides furfural, isophthalaldehyde and 3-phenyl-2-
292 propenal (cis-cinnamaldehyde) were perceived as bread, almond, sweet and cinnamon
293 odors. All of them had MF (%) around 40 and they were only found in one material.

294 Several acids like acetic, propanoic, butyric with their typical vinegar and rancid odors
295 were detected in PE2 and in two samples of PP (PP1 and PP3). They were important off-
296 odors with MF values (%) higher than 85 %. Reviewing the Figure 1a and Figure 1b, this
297 fact would coincide with rancid and vinegar attributes found for these samples in the
298 sensory analysis. Other acids detected in two PE materials with a lower MF (%) were
299 benzoic acid and nonanoic acid with urine and fat odor respectively.

300 Several terpenes were detected in the cardboards studies; they were l-limonene, b-pinene,
301 longyfolene and verbenone. They are natural compounds found in several resins of plants
302 like pine, that is used as raw material to manufacture the cardboard or paper. For this
303 reason, they could be the responsible for the odor attributes like woody, found in Figure
304 1c for these types of materials.

305 Other family of compounds had a ketone group in their structures, like for example
306 cyclohexanone, detected in the samples of paper and cardboard with a characteristic mint
307 odor and a MF (%) around 60. Other compounds such as 2- undecanone and 2-
308 tridecanone were found with MF (%) values of 84 and 58 respectively. They were
309 detected in PP4 with floral, fruity and green odors. Or acetophenone, above named,
310 detected in most of the samples as well as 3,4-dimethyl and 4-ethyl acetophenone, with a
311 floral odors, both found in the PP4.

312 Some alcohols were found in the samples studied. Linear alcohols like 2-ethyl-1-hexanol
313 (green odor) above mentioned and 1-octanol (moss and mushroom odors) were detected
314 in PP1 and PP2 samples with higher values of % MF than 80. This compound may be the
315 responsible for the moss odor found in the sensory assay for these samples (Figure 1a).
316 Also, 1-tridecanol and 1-tetradecanol were detected. They are used as lubricants as well
317 as for the manufacture of surfactants and plasticizers, and they were found in the sample
318 PP3 with must and coconut odor respectively.

319 Other aromatic alcohols found in PP and PE samples were phenol, used to synthesize
320 plastics and m-cresol as solvent. They had phenol and plastic odors respectively. Besides,
321 Benzene-methanol α -methyl was detected in one sample of cardboard 1 with a floral
322 perception.

323 Other compound detected was 4,5-dimethyl thiazole in PP3 with a nutty and soap odor.
324 Its functional use is as food additive for flavoring ingredient but nothing is found with the
325 appearance of this in PP material.

326 The rest of the compounds can be grouped into aromatic family composed of at least a
327 benzene ring into their structures. Toluene (paint odor), ethyl benzene (aromatic) and para
328 and orto xylene (plastic and geranium odors) used as solvents and they were found in
329 different PE and PP samples. Also, trimethyl benzenes were found in cardboard and paper
330 materials which may be generated by methylation of toluene and xylenes and be used as

331 sterilizing agents, gasoline additive or as solvent. They had plastic, oily and aromatic
332 odors and they may be the perpetrators of these attributes perceived in the sensory assay
333 for these materials.

334 Two compounds (anisole and estragole) had in their structures the benzene ring bond to
335 methoxy group. They were detected in two PP (PP1 and PP2) and they had aromatic,
336 phenolic and anise odors respectively. 4-phenyl-1-cyclohexene was detected in PE2 this
337 compound was also found in other work as off-odors in a fancy dress accessory handbag
338 for children (Wiedmer, Velasco-Schon, & Buettner, 2017).

339 Finally, two compounds were detected which had two benzene rings in their structures.
340 They were naphthalene and methylnaphthalene, both with tar odor and a high MF (%)
341 above 80%. It is worth noting that this odor attribute was previously perceived in the
342 sensory assay (Figure 1a) in some PP materials as well as in the paper and both
343 cardboards.

344

345 *3.3. Migration from odor compounds.*

346 The migration assay was carried out with Tenax ®, as above mentioned. After the
347 migration test, the extracts of Tenax ® were analyzed by GC-O-MS for two purposes.
348 Firstly, to sniff the samples and evaluate the migrants according to the MF (%) and
349 secondly, to calculate the concentration of the migrants in order to check if they were
350 below the specific migration limit (SML) and the values recommended by Cramer.

351 Analytical parameters of the GC–O–MS method are shown in Table 3. The limit of
352 detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ) and linear range for each compound are
353 expressed as µg of compound per Kg of simulant. Good results were obtained in terms of
354 linearity and limits of detection. LOD values were between 12 µg/Kg (ciclohexanone)
355 and 135 µg/Kg (acetic acid).

356 The migrant concentrations and their MF (%) for each material are also shown in Table
357 3. Migration values are expressed as µg compound per Kg of simulant. MF(%) values are
358 shown when they are higher than 20%, as was previously established.

359 Around fifty five percent of migration values were higher than their LOD or LOQ and a
360 forty six percent approximately of MF (%) were higher than 20.

361 Only nine migrated compounds appeared in the positive list of substances in the European
362 Regulation for plastics as contact materials. Two of which, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and phenol
363 have high SMLs corresponded to 30 and 3 mg/Kg (ppm) respectively and the rest of them
364 were authorized without limit of migration.

365 The rest of the compounds (thirty seven) didn't appear in the positive list of European
366 Regulation and then, due to lack of legislation, they were evaluated according to Cramer
367 class. Six compounds (4,5-dimethyl thiazole, durene, estragole, verbenone, naphthalene
368 and methyl naphthalene) were classified as Class III of toxicity and some ketones
369 (cyclohexanone, 2-undecanone and 2-tridecanone) corresponded to Class II.

370 Comparing the migration values, all compounds were below European legislation or
371 below the values recommended by Cramer according to their toxicities. Therefore, these
372 materials were safe for food contact applications.

373 However, when analyzing these migrations with the method GC-O-MS and calculating
374 their MF (%), important results were obtained.

375 In the sample PP1, the highest migration values, shown in the table 3, were obtained for
376 1-octanol and acetophenone 850 ± 76 and 488 ± 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$, respectively. The compounds
377 with $\text{MF}(\%) > 20$ were 1-octanol (58%), butyric acid (60%) and, anisole (33%) with
378 attributes like moss, rancid and aromatic odor. That it means, although all compounds
379 were safe for food contact materials, these migrations were perceived by the analysts with
380 high MF (%). Therefore, they could affect the organoleptic characteristics of packaged
381 food changing their properties.

382 Similar tendency was found for PP2, where the compounds with the highest migration
383 values were 1-octanol and anisole, obtaining also the highest MF (%) values, 56 and 32,
384 respectively. These values were similar to those obtained for PP1 and above mentioned.

385 In PP3, the migration of most of compounds and their MF% were below their LOQ and
386 their $\text{MF}(\%) < 20$. In contrast, propanoic acid migrated 415 ± 37 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ and its MF was
387 75%. This compound could be important because its rancid odor was perceived by a high

388 number of sniffers and with a high intensity after migration. Besides, its attributes were
389 already found in the previous sensory evaluation.

390 The aldehyde compounds such as octanal, nonanal and decanal had high MF (%) with
391 values 50, 45 and 52 % respectively for PP4, all of them with soap and fat descriptors.
392 This material had the highest number and concentration of compounds that migrated, with
393 a MF (%)>20, for example, p-xylene, durene, 2-undecanone, 4-isopropyl-benzaldehyde,
394 2-tridecanone and 4-ethylacetophenone, methylnaphthalene and tetradecanol. The
395 ketones group of compounds (2-undecanone and 2-tridecanone) had the highest values of
396 migration 578 ± 52 and 381 ± 31 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ but below 540 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ recommended by Cramer for
397 Class II of toxicity.

398 As above mentioned, in the migration of PE1, octanal, nonanal and decanal had the
399 highest MF (%) of 55, 55 and 50 % respectively. For PE2, acetic acid obtained the highest
400 value of MF (%) in all migration samples, as well as, phenol 60% of MF. The mean of
401 these results was very important, because after migration, these migrating compounds
402 were detected by sniffers with a high MF(%) and they had considerable relation-ship with
403 the attributes found in the previous sensory evaluation.

404 For the paper and cardboard samples, two groups of compounds with MF% >20 can be
405 underlined, one of them was aldehyde group with hexanal and nonanal with values
406 between 31 and 55%. Besides, with MF (%) between 35 and 43% trimethyl benzenes
407 were found. Also, the compounds longyfolene and verbenone were detected in the
408 cardboard 1 and 2 with MF% of 45, 36 and 45 (%).

409 Finally, it is important to emphasize that the compounds toluene, nonanal, 2-ethyl
410 hexanol, benzaldehyde and acetophenone, common in the plastic, paper and cardboard
411 materials under study, had migration values higher for paper and cardboard materials than
412 for PE and PP. This fact could be related with greater diffusion properties of the
413 compounds in these materials.

414

415 **4. Conclusion**

416 The off-odor compounds from different materials commonly used for food packaging
417 (PP, PE, paper and cardboard) have been evaluated. Firstly, a sensory evaluation has been

418 directly carried out in the materials as well as an analysis by GC-O- MS, in order to relate
419 previous sensorial attributes with the off-odor compounds identified by this technique.
420 This tool has proved to be very useful to identify a great number of odorous compounds.

421 Forty six compounds with characteristic odor have been identified: the most common
422 odorants found in most of the samples have been nonanal, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol,
423 benzaldehyde, acetophenone and naphthalene. Although the compounds with the
424 strongest odors were aldehydes with fat/soup odor in PP, PE and paper samples. Acetic,
425 propanoic and butyric with vinegar and rancid odors were found in PP samples. Terpenes
426 and trimethylbenzenes with woody, solvent and oily odors have been identified in
427 cardboard and paper samples.

428 Migration tests have been carried out and the same technique was applied to study the
429 off-odors.. The purpose was not only to quantify the migrant concentrations, in order to
430 evaluate possible human risk, but also, sniffing the migration samples to establish how
431 the organoleptic properties of packaged food could be affected. All identified migrant
432 compounds previously found were below both the limits of European Legislation and the
433 migration values recommended by Cramer. However, propanoic, acetic and butyric acid
434 as well as the aldehyde compounds (octanal, decanal, nonanal), phenol and 1-octanol
435 were detected by sniffers with high MF (%), between 50-78 (%), after the migration tests.

436 These results emphasize the importance of using this methodology to be capable to
437 highlight the off-odor migrant compound at very low concentration after the migration
438 tests (most of them below LOD and LOQ in MS but well perceived by olfactometry).
439 Even though the migration complies with the legislation and thus the materials do not
440 pose a risk for human health, they may affect the properties of the packaged food,
441 producing consumer complaints, higher production costs or even a possible loss of brand
442 confidence.

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446

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533

Table 1: Description of samples studied with their materials used and their purposes as food packaging materials

Samples studied	Description	Material	Code samples	Uses
Sample 1	Bag of plastic	Polypropylene	PP1	Cereals, flour and biscuits
Sample 2	Bag of plastic	Polypropylene	PP2	Dried fruit and vegetables.
Sample 2	Bag of paper with a transparent window	Paper Polypropylene	Paper1 PP2	Bread and pastry
Sample 3	Bag of plastic	Polypropylene	PP3	Dried pasta (macaroni, spaghetti..)
Sample 4	Bag of plastic	Polypropylene	PP4	Dried fruit and vegetables.
Sample 4	Bag of paper with a transparent window	Paper Polypropylene	Paper1 PP4	Bread and pastry
Sample 5	Bag of plastic with self-closing	Polyethylene of low density	PE1	Sandwich and biscuits to take away
Sample 6	Tetrabrick	Polypropylene of low density Cardboard	PE2 CB1	Sugar
Sample 7	Box	Cardboard	CB2	Eggs

Table 2: Odor compounds detected in the different materials ordered by their retention indexes. Their odors perceived as well as their modified frequency calculated for each material.

N°	Odorous compounds	IK	Odor	Material detected	FM
1	Toluene	1046	Paint	Paper1	55
				PP4	48
				Cardboard 1	60
2	Hexanal	1087	Fat, grass	Paper 1	82
				Cardboard 1	72
3	b-Pinene	1116	Resin	Cardboard 1	45
4	Ethyl benzene	1128	Aromatic	PE1	60
5	p-Xylene	1156	Plastic	PP4	82
				PE1	66
6	o-Xylene	1183	Geranium	PE1	42
7	Limonene	1203	Pine	Paper 1	55
				Cardboard 1	70
				Cardboard 2	74
8	1,2,4-trimethyl benzene	1276	Plastic, sweet	Cardboard 1	48
9	Octanal	1280	Fat, soap	PP4	90
				PE1	75
10	1,3,5-trimethyl benzene	1290	Oily, aromatic	Paper 1	45
				Cardboard 1	60
				Cardboard 2	52
11	Cyclohexanone	1308	Mint and acetone odor	Paper 1	55
				Cardboard 1	65
				Cardboard 2	63
12	1,2,3-trimethyl benzene	1337	Oily,aromatic	Cardboard 1	67
13	4,5-dimethyl thiazole	1380	Nutty, soap	PP3	43
14	1-octanol	1392	Moss, mushroom	PP1	82
				PP2	85
15	Nonanal	1395	Fat, citrus, green	Paper 1	85
				PP4	90
				PE1	92
				Cardboard 1	72
				Cardboard 2	78
16	Acetic acid	1451	Vinegar	PE2	95
17	Furfural	1457	Bread, almond	PE2	48
18	Durene	1469	Sweet	PP4	54
19	Decanal	1484	Soap	PP4	78
				PE1	69
20	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	1485	Green	PP1	65
				PP2	50
				PP3	55
				Paper 1	62
				Cardboard 1	43
				Cardboard 2	47
21	Longyfolene	1510	Woody	Cardboard 1	72
				Cardboard 2	69
22	Propanoic acid	1525	Rancid, pungent	PP3	96
23	Benzaldehyde	1542	Fruity, sweet, almond cherry	PP1	45
				PP2	58
				Paper 1	57
				PP3	52
				PE2	49
				Cardboard 1	42
24	2-undecanone	1595	Floral, fruity	Cardboard 2	61
				PP4	84

25	Butyric acid	1620	Cheese, Rancid	PP1 PP3	85 89
26	Benzoic acid	1640	Urine	PE1	45
27	Anisole	1654	Aromatic, phenolic	PP1 PP2	64 71
28	4-methyl-benzaldehyde	1654	cherry-like, sweet	PP3	43
29	Estragole	1658	Anise	PP1	40
30	Acetophenone	1671	Almond, flower	PP1	55
				PP4	58
				PE1	45
				PE2	45
				Paper 1	61
				Cardboard 1 Cardboard 2	66 54
31	4-ethyl-benzaldehyde	1722	Fruity	PP4	43
32	Verbenone	1733	Spicy odor and camphoraceous	Cardboard 1	57
33	Naphthalene	1770	Tar	PP1	66
				PP4	49
				Paper1	52
				Cardboard 1 Cardboard 2	61 55
34	P-isopropyl-benzaldehyde,	1799	Oily	PP4	46
35	2-Tridecanone	1807	Fruity, green	PP4	58
36	Benzenemethanol, α -methyl	1829	Floral	Cardboard 1	47
37	3,4-dimethylacetophenone	1863	Floral	PP4	44
38	4-ethylacetophenone	1868	Floral	PP4	58
39	Methylnaphthalene	1875	Tar	PP4	69
40	Tridecanol	1960	Moss	PP3	55
41	Phenol	1987	Phenol	PP3	42
				PE2	61
42	3-phenyl-2-propenal (Cinnamaldehyde)	2033	Cinnamon	PP3	40
43	2-tert-butyl-5-methyl phenol(m-cresol)	2130	Plastic	PP4	73
				PE1	45
44	Tetradecanol	2182	Coconut	PP3	42
45	Nonanoic acid	2204	Fat, green	PE2	62
46	Isophthalaldehyde	2341	Slight sweet	PP4	45

Table 3: Migration of odorous compounds previously identified, quantification ions (QI), analytical parameters as limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ) and linear range. Migration values for each material expressed as μg of compound per Kg of simulant. Modified frequently (MF%), SML according to European plastic legislation 10/2011 and toxicity class according to Cramer rules.

N°	Odorous compounds	QI	LOD	LOQ	Linear range $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$	Material detected	Migration $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$	FM	SML $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$	Cramer Class
1	Toluene	91	102	340	340-2300	Paper1	980±107	31		I
						PP4	514±46	<20		
						Cardboard 1	1340±190	35		
2	Hexanal	56	87	290	290-2500	Paper 1	353±28	55		I
						Cardboard 1	375±35	55		
3	b-Pinene	93	32	105	105-1030	Cardboard 1	657±63	<20		I
4	Ethyl benzene	91	16	53	53-650	PE1	175±16	24		I
5	p-Xylene	91	75	250	250-850	PP4	<LOD	33		I
						PE1	<LOD	30		
6	o-Xylene	91	75	250	250-850	PE1	<LOD	<20		I
7	Limonene	68	100	333	333-1500	Paper 1	<LOD	<20		I
						Cardboard 1	335±12	<20		
						Cardboard 2	<LOD	<20		
8	1,2,4-trimethyl benzene	105	18	60	60-850	Cardboard 1	230±12	35		I
9	Octanal	56	63	210	210-3050	PP4	<LOD	50		I
						PE1	<LOD	55		
10	1,3,5-trimethyl benzene	105	42	140	140-1080	Paper 1	<LOD	<20		I
						Cardboard 1	<LOQ	43		
						Cardboard 2	<LOQ	43		
11	Cyclohexanone	55	12	43	43-1030	Paper 1	<LOD	<20		II
						Cardboard 1	<LOD	<20		
						Cardboard 2	<LOD	<20		
12	1,2,3-trimethyl benzene	105	19	62	62-750	Cardboard 1	<LOQ	40		I
13	4,5-dimethyl thiazole	113	36	120	120-800	PP3	<LOD	<20		III
14	1-octanol	56	26	85	85-1090	PP1	850±76	58	Authorized without SML	
						PP2	892±133	56		
15	Nonanal	57	42	140	140-950	Paper 1	850±93	60		I
						PP4	<LOQ	45		
						PE1	523±58	55		
							230±22	33		

						Cardboard 1 Cardboard 2	303±29	31	
16	Acetic acid	60	135	450	450-2040	PE2	<LOQ	78	Authorized without SML
17	Furfural	96	66	220	220-1700	PE2	<LOD	<20	III
18	Durene	119	54	180	180-1050	PP4	255±23	33	I
19	Decanal	55	33	110	110-1200	PP4	413±40	52	I
						PE1	405±53	50	
20	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	57	47	156	156-2400	PP1	<LOQ	<20	SML=30000
						PP2	215±18	<20	
						PP3	<LOQ	<20	
						Paper 1	<LOD	<20	
						Cardboard 1	433±52	<20	
Cardboard 2	515±72	<20							
21	Longyfolene	161	*	*	*	Cardboard 1	622±92	45	
						Cardboard 2	505±40	36	
22	Propanoic acid	74	110	370	370-870	PP3	415±37	75	Authorized without SML
23	Benzaldehyde	77	22	73	73-950	PP1	181±16	<20	Authorized without SML
						PP2	235±31	<20	
						Paper 1	358±31	<20	
						PP3	285±19	<20	
						PE2	279±30	<20	
						Cardboard 1	342±29	<20	
Cardboard 2	410±37	<20							
24	2-undecanone	58	72	240	240-1800	PP4	578±52	45	II
25	Butyric acid	60	93	310	310-1070	PP1	<LOQ	60	Authorized without SML
						PP3	<LOQ	58	
26	Benzoic acid	105	30	95	95-980	PE1	<LOD	<20	Authorized without SML
27	Anisole	108	42	140	140-950	PP1	310±47	33	I
						PP2	325±52	32	
28	4-methyl-benzaldehyde	91	17	55	55-980	PP3	117±9	<20	I
29	Estragole	148	27	90	90-780	PP1	<LOQ	<20	III
30	Acetophenone	105	21	72	72-850	PP1	488±15	<20	I
						PP4	551±50	<20	

						PE1	255±26	<20	
						PE2	267±22	<20	
						Paper 1	732±59	<20	
						Cardboard 1	810±35	<20	
						Cardboard 2	623±60	<20	
31	4-ethyl-benzaldehyde	91	14	48	48-1010	PP4	<LOQ	<20	I
32	Verbenone	107	26	88	88-910	Cardboard 1	<LOQ	45	III
						PP1	<LOQ	<20	
						PP4	<LOD	<20	
33	Naphthalene	128	32	105	105-1400	Paper1	<LOD	<20	III
						Cardboard 1	<LOQ	<20	
						Cardboard 2	<LOQ	<20	
34	4-isopropyl-benzaldehyde	133	54	180	180-780	PP4	458±28	35	I
35	2-Tridecanone	58	75	250	250-1800	PP4	381±31	38	II
36	Benzenemethanol, α -methyl	79	28	95	95-780	Cardboard 1	455±41	<20	I
37	3,4-dimethylacetophenone	133	26	88	88-975	PP4	288±25	<20	I
38	4-ethylacetophenone	133	24	80	80-1050	PP4	584±53	39	I
39	Methylnaphthalene	128	39	130	130-1300	PP4	<LOQ	25	III
40	Tridecanol	55	22	75	75-540	PP3	<LOQ	25	I
41	Phenol	94	61	205	205-1900	PP3	<LOD	<20	
						PE2	415±39	41	SML=3000
42	3-phenyl-2-propenal (Cinnamaldehyde)	131	54	180	180-1700	PP3	<LOD	<20	I
43	2-tert-butyl-5-methyl phenol(m-cresol)	108	30	98	98-580	PP4	358±31	35	Authorized without SML
						PE1	<LOQ	<20	
44	Tetradecanol	55	57	190	190-650	PP3	<LOD	<20	I
45	Nonanoic acid	60	102	340	340-2800	PE2	<LOD	36	I
46	Isophthalaldehyde	134	33	110	110-850	PP4	<LOD	<20	I

*Quantified with the compound b-Pinene due to absence of commercial standard

Figure 1a: Spider diagram for PP samples with their characteristic odors and their intensities.

Figure 1b: Spider diagram for PE samples with their characteristic odors and their intensities.

Figure 1c: Spider diagrams for cardboard and paper materials with their characteristic odors and their intensities.

Figure 2: Chromatogram of GC-O-MS for the material Cardboard, analyzed by HS-SPME with the fiber DVB/CAR/PDMS (50/30 μm)